

COMPETENCIES OF MALARIA MICROSCOPISTS IN REGION 1: BASIS FOR A PROPOSED CAPABILITY ENHANCEMENT PROGRAM

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Competencies of Malaria Microscopists in Region 1: Basis for a Proposed Capability Enhancement Program

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of competencies of trained malaria microscopists on microscopy diagnostic components in Region I as a basis for a proposed capacity-building program. The study utilized quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive correlational approach. Purposive sampling was used to determine the number of respondents. Data were gathered using competency assessment tool using properly coded malaria slide panel and the competency of the microscopists on microscopy diagnostic components was determined with a research-made validated questionnaire. Results of the study revealed that the malaria microscopists in Region 1 come from varied but rich personal and professional background; are skilled and competent in performing malaria microscopic examination; and have experienced negligible challenges or difficulties and these do not affect their performance as microscopists. Furthermore, results indicate that the performance of malaria microscopists in Region 1 is not affected by their age, professional background, training and professional engagements, and their current employment credentials and that they are not disturbed by some minor difficulties they encounter in their laboratory activities. The research forwards a proposed capacity-building program that may be given to further enhance the skills of the malaria microscopists in Region 1.

Keywords: *level of competencies, trained malaria microscopists, capacity-building program*

Introduction

One of the most important needs of human beings is his/her security. This security comes from many factors that include financial security, emotional security, economic security, and health security. All of these make human beings' life bearable and enjoyable. Such that if one of these is compromised, human beings faced great challenges,

One of the many treats to the health security of human beings are the many diseases found in the community. Some of these are caused by the lifestyle; some by accidents; some by viruses and infections brought about by parasites and insects.

Malaria is a mosquito-borne disease caused by a parasite in the genus Plasmodium. Malaria is a parasitic infection caused by the intracellular protozoa of Plasmodium species namely *P. falciparum*, *P. vivax*, *P. ovale*, *P. malariae* and *P. knowlesi*. Among all Plasmodium species *P. falciparum* remains the most common cause of severe malaria and responsible for majority of deaths due to malaria globally. *P. vivax* and *P. ovale* cause relapsing malaria, whereas *P. malariae* can present with late recrudescence after several years (Andronesco et al., 2023). Generally, people with malaria often experience fever, chills, and flu-like illness. If left untreated, the infection in its most severe forms can lead to permanent learning disabilities, coma, and death.

Indeed, malaria is a life-threatening disease primarily found in tropical countries caused by parasites that are transmitted to people through the bites of infected female Anopheles mosquitoes. Malaria is one of the most prevalent parasitic infections threatening millions of people in tropical and subtropical countries. The disease, according to the 2022 WHO report, affected 247 million people globally and caused 619,000 deaths in 2021, increasing from 229 million cases and 409,000 deaths in 2019 (Gil et al., 2023).

Specifically, reports show that malaria is a leading cause of mortality globally, particularly among children under five years of age (Milner et al., 2020). This supports the report of Boivin, et al. stating that children under five years have a higher risk of acquiring malaria and are more likely to experience severe adverse effects compared to children over five years. In addition, according to Suh et al. (2023), in areas with high transmission, the most vulnerable groups are young children, who have not developed immunity to malaria yet, and pregnant women, whose immunity has been decreased by pregnancy.

The devastating impact of malaria cannot be underestimated, especially as it affects poor and underserved people worldwide, especially that malaria occurs mostly in poor tropical and subtropical areas of the world. Moreover, the costs of malaria – to individuals, families, communities, and nations – are indeed enormous (Afia et al., 2022). This possibility is caused by the fact that poor children and women in rural areas are at the greatest risk of death or severe debility from malaria, which drains the resources of families.

These situations lead to the inclusion of malaria to many illnesses that have gravely affected the public health, especially in many African countries and some Asian countries. In fact, malaria, according to Dufera et al. (2020), remains the third leading cause of death and is still considered a major public health problem in countries like Western Ethiopia.

Furthermore, the occurrence of malaria has also affected the economy of affected countries like the malaria-stricken Africa. Leading economists estimate that malaria causes an "economic growth penalty" of up to 1.3% per year in malaria endemic African countries (Haakestad et al., 2019). Malaria discourages investments and tourism, affects land use patterns and crop selection, resulting in sub-optimal agricultural production, reduces labor productivity, and impairs learning (Andrade et al., 2022).

According to 2023 report of Johns Hopkins Bloomberg School of Public Health, Center for Communication Programs, the economic impact of malaria is estimated to cost Africa \$12 billion every year. This figure factors in costs of health care, absenteeism, days lost in education, decreased productivity due to brain damage from cerebral malaria, and loss of investment and tourism.

In an article of Ricci (2012) entitled *Social Implications of Malaria and Their Relationships with Poverty*, it was emphasized that Some evidence suggests that malaria also leads to lower labor productivity by contributing to the prevalence of anemia among poor households. Further, malaria also might contribute to malnutrition and low birth weight. This, in conjunction with reduced learning among children who suffer repeated episodes of malaria, might lead to lower levels of human capital among households in malaria-endemic communities.

Moreover, malaria has made a very significant impact on the education of many children. In an article written by Lehbun (2022) entitled, *The Impact of Malaria on Children's Education*, she claimed that children exposed to malaria may experience severe cognitive and educational setbacks. She also highlighted the impact of malaria to schoolchildren, citing the result of the research study conducted by University of Maryland School of Medicine (UMSOM) in Malawi and Mali, which pointed out that clinical malaria, causes school absences, anemia and limits cognitive development. The combination of all these factors contribute to both decreased cognitive function as well as decreased educational attainment.

Asia ranks second to Africa in terms of malaria burden. In 19 countries of Asia, malaria is endemic and 2.31 billion people or 62% of the total population in these countries are at risk of malaria (Bhatia et al., 2013). Supporting this claim, Cheng et al. (2021) emphasized that despite achieving notable decreases in morbidity and mortality, malaria remains an important disease burden in the region. Nearly 8 million combined cases of malaria were reported across Brunei, Cambodia, Indonesia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, the Philippines, Singapore, Thailand, and Vietnam. According to the World Health Organization (WHO) global malaria report, the Western Pacific Region had an estimated 1.7 million cases in 2019 with 52% reduction in the number of deaths in about 2 decades.

The Philippines, as part of the Asian countries identified to be at risk for malaria cases, has committed itself to attain a malaria-free Philippines by 2030 - this is the Government's target in the National Malaria Control and Elimination Program (NMCEP). True to its commitment, despite the pandemic, the Philippine Department of Health, in its April 26, 2021 report, highlighted that the Philippines has significantly reduced the incidence of malaria by 87% from 48,569 in 2003 to 6,120 cases in 2020. The country has also reported a 98% reduction in the number of mortality due to malaria, from 162 deaths in 2003 to 3 deaths in 2020 (Department of Health, 2021). Corollary to this, the Health Department also reported that all provinces in the country have achieved malaria-free status except for Palawan, which the Department aims to clear until 2026.

The tall order to make the entire Philippines malaria-free by 2030 requires a nation-wide collaboration to prevent malaria. The public must be made aware of the endemic areas; be educated on the prevention of mosquito bites by wearing long-sleeved clothes and using insect repellants and mosquito nets; get prophylactic treatment when traveling to endemic areas; and seek immediate medical consultation if symptoms of malaria are observed.

This also involves the need for the upskilling the competence of malaria microscopists (some are medical technologists; some trained community health workers) who are expected to deliver early diagnosis and prompt treatment of malaria. They conduct manual microscopic examinations to determine the occurrence of malaria cases. Microscopic examination remains the gold standard for laboratory confirmation of malaria in the malaria-endemic world. To date, many government and private health facilities rely on malaria microscopy for malaria diagnosis (Jemere et al., 2018). In addition, the malaria microscopists are expected to be at the forefront in offering prompt and precise diagnosis and effective treatment. Microscopic examination of Giemsa-stained blood films continues to be widely used for parasitological confirmation of malaria diagnosis.

Worldwide, Health Departments face a dilemma concerning the number of qualified and competent microscopists who will conduct microscopic examinations. This is aside from the fact that there is a scarcity of qualified laboratory professionals for correctly diagnosing malaria using microscopy (Jemere et al., 2018). Microscopists, in accordance with the guidelines of malaria microscopy quality assurance, which were introduced by WHO in 2016, need to be trained and be certified for a period valid for 3 years (Akiko-Matsumoto et al. 2021).

In the Philippines, the Research Institute for Tropical Medicine (RITM) Parasitology Department was designated WHO Collaborating Center for Malaria diagnosis since 2011. The Center currently houses the National Reference Laboratory for Malaria and Other Parasite. The center serves as the training facility of WHO is capacitating the malaria microscopists in the country. With the call to end malaria in all parts of the Philippines by 2030, there is a stronger call to make the malaria microscopists more adept to the processes of clinical microscopic examinations and be more updated with the trends in malaria diagnosis and treatment.

Considering the foregoing and the fact that the diagnosis of malaria is still largely relying on the clinical presentation (Prescott, 2012; Akiko-Matsumoto, et al., 2021), reliable laboratory diagnosis is essential for effective malaria case management and to evaluate the impact of malaria control interventions (WHO, 2010). Moreover, laboratory professionals are not always consistent with malaria diagnosis results. At times, their performance gets affected by the length of time needed for examining a single slide and lack of training and quality control programmers (Ngasala & Bushukatale, 2019). In addition, quality control (QC) program for malaria microscopy is not adequately developed for evaluation of each laboratory professionals in malaria diagnosis (WHO, 2009).

The provinces of Region 1 have made sustainable programs to end malaria. In 2017, the Provincial Government of La Union (PGLU) received recognition from the Department of Health (DOH) for achieving the Malaria-free status. The same recognition was accorded to the provinces of Ilocos Norte and Pangasinan. In addition, the province of Ilocos Sur was also declared malaria-free in 2018. The four provinces in Region 1 have made sustainable efforts to implement malaria elimination programs. These are carried out by the concerted efforts of the local government units, the health care professionals, and with the expertise of malaria microscopists.

In the Region I, as of 2023, there are sixty (60) malaria microscopists. All of them are licensed medical technologists from the different government and private hospitals and selected Rural Health Units in the province. They are equipped with certificate of training on Basic Malaria Microscopy, which was conducted by World Health Organization Certified Core of Trainers (WHO certified) from the Malaria Collaboration and Training Center for North Luzon Cluster, Tuguegarao, Cagayan. To maintain the competency level of microscopists, it is essential to have effective skill-based trainings and periodic assessment or monitoring of performance and that they need to be equipped with the knowledge and skills necessary for establishing standards in advanced malaria microscopy. This is aligned to the recommendation of Ngasala and Bushukatale (2019) on the conduct of regular in-service training and external quality assessments at private health facilities to enhance the skills of private health facility microscopists in malaria microscopy. This further the recommendations of several researchers (Bell et al., 2016; Alombah, et al. 2019) on the need for training of microscopists and supportive supervision to improve malaria microscopy competencies in health facilities.

Hence, this study was conceptualized to determine the competencies of malaria microscopists in Region 1 as basis of identifying a continuous professional updating initiative in the form of enhancement capability program to sustain the drive to make the province, the Region, and the entire Philippines malaria-free by 2030.

Research Questions

The study determined the level of competencies of trained malaria microscopists on microscopy diagnostic components in Region I as a basis for a proposed enhancement capability program. Specifically, the study answered the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. sex;
 - 1.2. age;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. years in service;
 - 1.5. status of employment;
 - 1.6. relevant trainings/seminars attended for the past three years;
 - 1.7. position; and
 - 1.8. score in the malaria microscopy panel slide examinations?
2. What is the level of competencies of microscopists along the following microscopy diagnostic components:
 - 2.1. preparation;
 - 2.2. making malaria smears;
 - 2.3. staining; and
 - 2.4. slide examination?
3. What are the challenges encountered by malaria microscopists along the Microscopy Diagnostic?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competency of the microscopists on the microscopy diagnostic components and the respondents' profile?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the problems encountered by malaria microscopists and respondents' profile

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative research design, specifically the descriptive correlational approach. Descriptive correlational research, according to Creswell (2018) is a type of research design that tries to explain the relationship between two or more variables without making any claims about cause and effect. It includes collecting and analyzing data on at least two variables to see if there is a link between them.

Further, the research approach was used to clearly describe the determine level of competencies of trained malaria microscopists on microscopy diagnostic components in Region I.

Participants

The study dealt with the level of competencies on microscopy diagnostic components of trained malaria microscopists in Region I. Hence, purposive sampling to determine the participants was considered in the study. The main goal of purposive sampling, according to Black (2010), is to identify the cases, individuals, or communities' best suited to helping you answer your research question.

Hence, the study considered the entire population of malaria microscopists in Region 1 as the respondents of the study and therefore,

no sampling technique was employed. Since the entire population was considered in this study, no identification of exclusion or inclusion criteria was done.

In the Region I, as of 2023, there are sixty (60) malaria microscopists. All of them are licensed medical technologists from the different government and private hospitals and selected Rural Health Units in the province. Collection of data was conducted on October, 2023.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher requested permission to conduct a study from the concerned respondents. An official request letter from the Dean, Institute of Graduate and Advanced Studies was sought to formalize the conduct of the study.

The malaria microscopists as the respondents of the study were given one-on-one face-to-face orientation on the purpose of the study and their role in the conduct of the study. Each malaria microscopist was given a questionnaire to answer and coded malarial slides to examine. There was a total of 15 coded malarial slides, of which 10 of these slides contain specimens positive with malaria parasite specie/s and five (5) with negative malaria parasite specie/s. The respondents were given an adequate and acceptable timeframe to work on the slides. Using the Malaria Microscopy Quality Assurance (MMQA) form, the respondents were required, if the slide will contain positive specie/s of a malarial parasite, to specify the malaria to be falciparum or vivax, malariae in case of single infection. In case of or multiple infection or the presence of two (2) or more species in a single slide, the microscopist were required to indicate the answer in the answer following specific legends such as F for plasmodium falciparum, V for pjasmodium vivax, M for pjasmodium malariae, and NMPS for negative/absence of parasite/ No malaria parasite seen. Moreover, for mixed infection, the codes: FV for plasmodium falciparum and plasmodium vivax and FM for plasmodium falciparum ang piasmodium malariae were used as codes.

All malaria microscopists were required to submit the results of their diagnosis after the given timeframe. Upon submission at the DOH CHD I, the accomplished MMQA form were assessed through the answer key, which was used as guide in checking the results of the microscopist reading.

In addition, upon submission of the results of their diagnosis, they were asked to answer the questionnaire. The researcher administered the questionnaire personally.

Data Analysis

The results of the assessment of the submitted slides were the bases in identifying the level of competency of malaria microscopists in identifying and differentiating malarial parasites. On the other hand, to determine the challenges encountered by the malaria microscopists, frequency counts were done and simple means shall be computed to determine the intensity of the problem or challenge of the possible factors that may affect the submission of accurate diagnosis/ specimen reading. These factors were ranked using a scale of 1 to 5 (5 being the most intense/challenging factor). The range using five-point Likert-scale to rank the challenges was conceptualized as the respondents were asked to allow the respondents freedom to select the simplest to most pressing problems from the given list; they, too, were given freedom to list other possible challenges that were not included in the list. The scale was then used in determining the difficulties the respondents faced as they exercise their roles as microscopists.

The identified problems or challenges served as an add-on basis for designing a capacity building program to enhance their competence level and further harness their diagnostic skills relative to the identification and differentiation of malarial parasites. To answer the significant relationship between the variables, Multiple Linear Regression will be utilized.

Ethical Considerations

In the conduct of the study, the researcher informed the malaria microscopists on the purpose and other important details of the study. Proper coordination was relayed to the concerned professionals relative to the schedule of interviews and the interpretation of its results. The researcher applied the principles of intellectual honesty and integrity in gathering the data essential for the study, as well as, in the acknowledgment of references, published or unpublished, with the appropriate form and style.

In the data-gathering process, the researcher assured all the participants of the confidentiality of the data gathered from them. To cover their identity, their names were not mentioned in the discussion; codes were used instead. The participants of the study were not subjected to any form of physical, emotional, or psychological harm. The plagiarism rule was observed since all references and materials to be used will be properly cited and documented.

Results and Discussion

In this present study, the respondents are the malaria microscopists from the four provinces in Region I that includes Pangasinan, La Union, Ilocos Sur, and Ilocos Norte. The term “microscopist” refers to a community health worker who is trained as a microscopist and diagnoses malaria in febrile patients using a microscope and prescribes first-line anti-malarial drugs when patients have malaria.

Part I. Profile of Respondents

The profile of these malaria microscopists that are included in this study include their age, sex, highest educational attainment, years of service, status of employment, relevant trainings attended, position, and their scores in malaria microscopy panel slide examination.

Table 1. *Profile of Respondents*

Profile of the Respondents along Age		
Age	N	%
20-30 years old	6	10.00
31-40 years old	16	26.67
41-50 years old	20	33.33
51-60 years old	13	21.67
61 years old and above	5	8.33
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Sex		
Male	11	18.33
Female	49	81.67
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Highest Educational Attainment		
Highest Educational Attainment		
College Graduate	54	90.00
With MA unit	2	3.33
Master's Degree Holder	4	6.67
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Years in Service		
Years In Service		
1-3 years	7	11.67
4-6 years	21	35.00
7-9 years	8	13.33
10 years and above	24	40.00
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Status of Employment		
Status of Employment		
Contract of Service	5	8.33
Permanent	55	91.67
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Relevant Trainings Attended		
Basic Malaria Microscopy	22	36.67
Refresher Course on Malaria Microscopy	36	60.00
Malaria Validator's Training	5	8.33
No Relevant Training at All	6	10.00
Total	60	100
Profile of the Respondents along Position		
Position		
Medical Technologist I	28	46.67
Medical Technologist II	22	36.67
Medical Technologist III	2	3.33
Medical Technologist IV	1	1.67
Medical Laboratory Aide	2	3.33
Medical Laboratory Technician I	4	6.67
Medical Laboratory Technician II	1	1.67
Total	60	100
Score in the Malaria Microscopy Panel Slide Examination		
11.00 – 15.00 (Competent)	40	66.67
6.00 – 10.99 (Moderately Competent)	18	30.00
1.00 – 5.99 (Poorly Competent)	2	3.33
Total	60	100

Legend: N: frequency %: ratio expressed as a fraction of 100

Age. Table 1.1 presents the age profile of the 60 malaria microscopists in Region 1. As gleaned from the table, about a third ($n=20$ or 33.33%) of the respondents belong the age group of 41-50, which means that the respondents are middle-aged and of matured age and this signifies that they have attained wisdom and maturity through the years. This age group implies that the respondents have gained enough maturity and experience that they can use in fulfilling their tasks and responsibilities as malaria microscopists.

Among research conducted involving health workers, some results reveal that age was one of the variables that satisfactory and significantly impact job performance (Zaman et al., 2022). Corollary to this, in a separate study involving frontline health workers conducted by Naqvi and Faryal (2023), results demonstrated that age has significant positive correlation with job performance.

The findings of this study are consistent with those of Lakshimita et al.'s (2019) study, which discovered that age has a favorable and

significant impact on work productivity. In addition, they assert that as workers get older and more productive, so does their level of output.

Sex. Table 1.2 presents the sex profile of the 60 malaria microscopists in Region 1. From the table, it could be gleaned that a huge majority of the respondents are female ($n=49$ or 89.67%). This means that the health profession does not discriminate sexes and that gender biases do not have a place among health professionals. This finding negates the claims of Raypole (2022) stating that gender bias shows up in laboratories when men are often automatically perceived as better and lead researchers.

As healthcare professionals working in the community, they too, are expected to implement community awareness-raising activities aimed at preventing transmission of malaria among their patients and their patients' families and to provide some forms of counseling to their patients and some researches show that the sex of the healthcare professional matters. In addition, in the study of Crispin et al. (2012) it was found out that female health workers tend to more likely provide counsel to their clients appropriately than the males.

Highest Educational Attainment. Table 1.3 reflects the profile of the respondents along their highest educational attainment. As gleaned on the table, a huge majority of the respondents ($n=54$ or 90.00%) are bachelor's degree holders, and that a very small percentage have endeavored to attain higher level of studies. This means that the respondents have entry or basic qualifications to be a microscopist having obtained the fundamental competencies in their undergraduate exposure in laboratories and other similar platforms.

However, this result implies the need for the microscopists to continue their professional development to keep themselves abreast with the recent developments and innovations in the field, which can be shared by experts through their academic engagements and sharing in the classrooms. This conforms to the findings of Abun et al. (2021), citing that the higher the educational attainment, the more likely it is to have higher self-efficacy, and that variation in self-efficacy is directly affected by the educational attainment. Similarly, higher educational attainment can lead to more attractive job opportunities (Dickson & Harmon, 2011), greater labor force flexibility (Solomon, 2021), and more rewarding jobs (Oreopoulos & Salvanes, 2011).

The need for microscopists to attain a higher degree of education is also highlighted in the study of Nega et al. (2020), stating that the performance of participants with a master's degree have higher percent agreement on parasite detection than participants with a bachelor's degree and Diploma certificate. In addition, as mentioned in the study of Crispin, et al., higher levels of education were associated with good record keeping and are expected to have appropriately provided counsel to their clients than their lower literacy level counterparts.

Years in Service. Table 1.4 reflects the profile of the respondents along years of service. From the table, it can be gleaned that most ($n=24$ or 40.00%) of the respondents have been in the service for more than 10 years which is closely followed by those with 4-6 years in service ($n=21$ or 35.00%). This result indicates that the microscopists have gained experience over the years, which can be translated to better skill in performing microscopy in general and in detecting and identifying malarial parasites, in particular.

The finding runs parallel to the study of Nega (2020) citing that participants skill also differs based on the experience years; the higher the service year the higher is participants' capacity to detect and identify parasites.

Status of Employment. Table 1.5 presents the profile of the microscopists along their status of employment. From the table, it could be deduced that a great majority of the respondents are of permanent status ($n=55$ or 91.67%) which means that they are enjoying full benefits and other privileges from their employment as healthcare professionals or microscopists. This implies that the respondents have the qualifications required by the government, which allowed them to receive plantilla item to serve the community as malaria microscopists.

Furthermore, in reference to their current position as malaria microscopists, most of them are licensed medical technologists and are occupying the position as Medical Technologists. Such data can prove that these are the basic qualifications to get a permanent status of employment in the government sector. This also implies that by being licensed medical technologists, they are capable in performing microscopy and have high capacity to perform laboratory activities leading to differentiation and identification.

Accordingly, Matsumoto-Takahashi and Kano (2016) explained that high-capacity microscopists could be expected to offer high service quality (active detection, diagnosis and treatment, prescription of anti-malarial, and follow-up) and to show a high level of ability in malaria microscopy (preparation and documentation, slide preparation and observation, safe handling and disposal, and knowledge on the morphology of infected red blood cells).

Relevant Trainings Attended. Table 1.6 presents the profile of the microscopists along their training attended. From the table, it could be deduced that a majority of the respondents have attended a Refresher Course on Malaria Microscopy ($n=36$ or 60.00%) which means that they have been equipped themselves with the skills and competence on conducting malaria microscopy making them qualified for the position. This implies that the respondents have attained competencies in conducting malaria microscopy which they have gained from the refresher course they have attended from certified microscopists and was conducted by the Department of Education.

According to the Department of Health, the training on competency-based training on malaria microscopy provided the participants with the knowledge and skills necessary for establishing standards in advanced malaria microscopy in their respective facilities. The training and their qualifications coupled with their knowledge and skills that are imparted to the participants are grounded on the World

Health Organization (WHO) Malaria Microscopy Learners Guide Training Manual.

According to the Guidelines in the Implementation of the Quality Assurance System of Malaria Microscopy in the Philippines, mandates the head of the health facility providing diagnostic services for malaria shall identify/designate staff to perform malaria microscopy and make the necessary administrative and financial arrangements for the designated staff to participate in a Basic Malaria Microscopy Training Course. Along this line, the medical technologist shall undergo a 2-week Basic Malaria Microscopy Training while non-medical technologist shall undergo 5-week Basic Malaria Microscopy Training.

This implies that the microscopists have put premium and value on their professional development. Professional development is important because it has the potential to open opportunities for career advancement. Continuing professional development (CPD) is central to professionals' (including healthcare workers) lifelong learning and constitutes a vital aspect of keeping nurses' knowledge and skills up-to-date (Mlambo et al., 2021).

The need for continuous professional development is essential to be equipped with technical expertise on dealing with the challenges that their work may give. Community health workers' programs usually face a myriad of challenges including lack of professional training in health (Brown, et. al. 2006). With highly trained and experienced microscopists, it can offer reliable results and enable identification and quantification of sexual and asexual stages of infections by different malaria parasite species.

Position. Table 1.7 presents the profile of the microscopists along their position. From the table, it could be gleaned that 55 of the 60 (91.67%) are holding the position as Medical Technologists. A closer look at the table shows that a good number of the respondents are Medical Technologist I (n=28 or 46.67%) that means the respondents have attained the basic qualifications to be malaria microscopists. This is immediately followed by those occupying the position of Medical Technologist II (n=22 or 36.67%).

The result also implies that these healthcare professional or medical technologists, supported by their trainings, can be able to diagnose different malaria parasites species by microscopy within international recommended standards. Their qualifications can help them identify the stages and species of malaria parasite and the density of infection, enabling the physician to treat a patient with the most appropriate antimalarial agents.

Score in the Malaria Microscopy Panel Slide Examination. Table 2 presents the scores garnered by the 60 respondents in the conduct of malaria microscopy panel slide examination. A perusal of the overall performance of the microscopists shows that 56 of the 60 (93.33%) microscopists passed the slide examination with five of them getting the perfect score.

Table 2. *Score in the Malaria Microscopy Panel Slide Examination*

<i>Score in the Malaria Microscopy Panel Slide Examination</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>%</i>
11.00 – 15.00 (Competent)	40	66.67
6.00 – 10.99 (Moderately Competent)	18	30.00
1.00 – 5.99 (Poorly Competent)	2	3.33
Total	60	100

From the analysis, it could be gleaned further that a huge majority (n=40 or 66.67%) of the have managed to register a score described as competent or a score range from 11.00 – 15.00. This means that the malaria microscopists have the right competence and skills to conduct malaria microscopy. This further means that their training and their educational qualifications have been factors to the very good performance in microscopy – including differentiation.

Prescott (2012) explained that malaria microscopy is a skill that requires considerable training, experience and practice to achieve and maintain proficiency. Even to make the measurement of that proficiency consistent and fair is a daunting task. While examining a blood film, the well-trained microscopist looks at and integrates other aspects of the hematology being examined into the diagnosis. In addition, accurate early diagnosis and prompt treatment are one of the key strategies to control and prevent malaria disease (Sori et al., 2018).

Part II. Level of Competencies of Microscopists along Microscopy Diagnostic Components

The laboratory comprises an invaluable part of the total health care provided to patients. In modern health care, laboratory analyses are essential tools in securing accurate diagnoses and in providing appropriate treatments and follow-ups. As such, competencies of health care professionals, including the malaria microscopists who perform a range of laboratory assays, are crucial to forming diagnoses and treatment protocols.

Competency in microscopy is the ability of a microscopist to examine malaria blood film and report the results accurately. Along this line, an appropriate and accurate diagnosis for the detection of malaria parasites has been a longstanding challenge for epidemiological screening and surveillance to provide information on malaria control strategies to reduce morbidity and mortality.

As such, it is imperative that malaria microscopists be competent along areas of microscopic diagnostic components that include preparation, making malaria smears, staining, and slide examination.

Table 3. *Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Preparation*

	Mean	DE
clean and handle object glasses properly according to the standards of DOH/ WHO	3.77	HC
utilize frosted-end object glasses properly and carefully	3.75	HC
identify carefully patients by observing protocols on patient marking and identification	3.77	HC
utilize effectively and conscientiously laboratory utilities and equipment in the conduct of microscopy	3.75	HC
label properly slides before performing actual analysis to avoid medical errors	3.87	HC
observe and promote the proper use, care, and maintenance of microscope	3.73	HC
Sub-Mean	3.77	HC

Legend: HC = Highly Competent

Preparation

As gleaned on Table 3, the level of competency of the respondents along preparation of the laboratory registered a mean of 3.77 and is described to be highly competent. This result means that the microscopists are generally proficient and skilled in ensuring that the pre-work activities are in place to secure and maintain a hygienic working environment. This implies that the microscopists acknowledge the need to make the laboratory and all its apparatuses clean, safe, and secure to avoid cross contamination and to minimize, if not to completely remove, all hazards and risks that may tamper the result of the microscopy.

Specifically, among the indicators, the microscopists were found to be highly competent on putting proper labels on the slides before performing actual analysis. This yields a mean of 3.87. This finding goes to show that they are so conscious of their work and that failure for them to do proper markings and labels may create more problems that may cause havoc in diagnosis and later on, treatment of patient. This greatly indicates that they are so careful in attaining medical errors and this result clearly indicates that they advocate the elimination of medical errors that is very important for pathologists and microscopists.

This supports the contention of Rodziewicz, Houseman, and Hipskind (2023) stating that all health professionals know medical errors create a serious public health problem that poses a substantial threat to patient safety. In a wider perspective, medical errors can tarnish the reputation of the healthcare institution and the workers (Robertson & Long, 2018).

In related study of Layfield and Anderson (2010), it was reported that medical errors involved patient name, and site and that majority of mislabeling occurred in the gross room or laboratory where specimens are processed and handled. Moreover, Medical errors, as reported by Oyeboade (2013), are a serious public health problem and a leading cause of death in the United States.

Hence, it is vital for the malarial microscopists to observe proper labelling of slides to avoid any form of medical errors that can cause lives of patients and their license as healthcare professionals.

On the other hand, the microscopists, although still found to be highly competent with the mean rating of 3.73, were found to be lagging among the six indicators on the observance and promotion of the proper use, care, and maintenance of microscope. This means that, still, they are after the proper utilization and safeguard of the equipment in their working environment and that these are given extra care and attention. It implies that each microscopist is aware of the need to take extra care of their laboratory equipment as the regular maintenance and upkeep of this equipment is necessary for accurate diagnosis and in overall facilitation of their duties and responsibilities as malaria microscopists. Furthermore, this also implies that the microscopists are after the attainment of an optimal microscope performance that requires regular maintenance and quality control testing. Microscopes should be set up for optimal performance, protected from damage, used ergonomically, regularly maintained and, if required, repaired by qualified personnel.

This result is also in compliance to Malaria Microscopy Standard Operating Procedure – MM-SOP-12 released by the World Health Organization in 2016. In the said operating procedure manual, the WHO categorically stated that the accuracy of malaria microscopy depends on the correct functioning and use of the microscope.

Making Malaria Smears

Malaria parasites are identified with the microscopists examining a drop of the patient's blood, spread out as a “blood smear” on a microscope slide. Microscopy, an integral process in malaria diagnosis, requires careful and efficient visualization of the malaria parasites in a blood smear of the patient. As such, making malaria smears is an important skill every malarial microscopist must have.

Aside from the Table 11 below, the level of competency of malarial microscopists along making malaria smears is described as highly competent, with a mean rating of 3.72. This means that they have attained the required expertise and relevant skill in doing malaria blood samples and spread out as a “blood smear” on a microscope slide as an input to the proper determination of possible malaria cases. This also means that they are very competent to do diagnosis and eventually prevent the occurrence of more chaotic health and malarial conditions.

This finding implies that they can properly manage the conduct of microscopic examination. Optical microscopy examination of blood smears is the gold standard technique for malaria diagnosis (Rubio et al., 2022). In like manner, Yu et al. (2022) agreed with the latter, stating that laboratory techniques for malaria diagnosis by detecting Plasmodium parasites are extensively used worldwide; microscopic visualization of thin and thick blood smears is the gold standard technique for malaria diagnosis.

Among the indicators, the item asking if the microscopists observe proper labeling of malaria blood smears/films was rated the highest with a mean rating of 3.82, described as highly competent. This means that the microscopists are aware of the protocol to properly safeguard the specimen gathered by putting appropriate labels and tags to avoid cross contamination and possibly misdiagnosis.

In relation to this, according to Yang et al. (2019), proper and correct labeling of malaria blood films is important to ensure that the sample and the data correspond to the patient. The integrity of the diagnosis may be compromised by unlabeled or wrongly labeled blood films. Thus, incorrectly labelled or erroneous markings in malaria blood smears may lead to in appropriate health care provision that may lead to patient death.

Table 4. Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Making Malaria Smears

	Mean	DE
prepare blood smears as soon as possible after blood collection	3.67	HC
prepare at least 2 smears per patient (thin and thick smears)	3.68	HC
collect a minimum blood sample volume of 2 mL for every adult patient	3.75	HC
differentiate thick and thin smears properly	3.75	HC
observe the collection of 2-3 small drops of blood and use them to make the thick film.	3.68	HC
use the slide to collect a small drop of blood and use it to make the thin film.	3.72	HC
observe properly labeling of malaria blood smears/films	3.82	HC
Sub-Mean	3.72	HC

Legend: HC = Highly Competent

Patient safety is the foundation of high-quality health care, as recognized both nationally and worldwide. Patient blood specimen identification is critical in ensuring the delivery of safe and appropriate care. Furthermore, this finding is anchored on the finding of (Duteau, 2014), stating that misidentified samples due to labeling errors create a serious risk to patient safety, leading to multiple specimen withdrawals, delay in diagnosis, misdiagnosis, incorrect treatment, transfusion reactions, increased length of stay and other negative patient outcomes.

On the other hand, the indicator that registered the lowest mean rating of 3.67, described as highly competent, is the indicator on the preparation blood smears as soon as possible after blood collection. This means that, although they are still of good competence and skills in doing the action, the microscopists experience a delay in the actual preparation of the blood samples collected for smearing and analysis. This finding implies that the microscopists may be taking their time to send the blood samples to laboratory or to have these be analyzed.

This may further imply that the microscopists may not be fully aware of the need to process the fresh blood samples for smearing and of the possible ill effects of not preparing blood smears within the fastest time possible. Thus, this posts risks and possible misdiagnosis because of specimen mishandling due to time constraints. This is aligned with the fact that artifacts of specimen handling and preparation can significantly impair examination of blood cells.

This is also the contention of Adewoyin and Nwogoh (2014) stating that samples should be sent to the laboratory as soon as possible. Samples are best analyzed within 2 hours of blood collection. Delay in preparation of blood smear may allow for the degeneration of the cellular elements of blood and may result in a pseudo-thrombocytopenia (falsely reduced platelet count) due to formation of platelet aggregates. Accordingly, Quang (2021) stated that there are various factors affecting blood smear preparation, such as the amount of time collected blood samples.

Staining

The World Health Organization (WHO) provides protocols for the diagnosis of malaria. One of them is related to the staining process of blood samples to guarantee the correct parasite visualization. The Giemsa stain is used as the gold standard for the diagnosis of malaria on blood smears. As mentioned by Das, et al. (2020) microscopy of stained blood films is essential for the diagnosis of malaria, differentiation of parasite species, and estimation of parasite density performed for assessments of antimalarial drug efficacy.

Table 5. Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Staining

	Mean	DE
observe the proper procedure in preparing the buffer and Giemsa stock solution	3.65	HC
ensure that the staining solution is freshly prepared or filtered before use.	3.62	HC
perform proper staining of malaria blood films with Giemsa – avoid over or under-staining	3.68	HC
observe the procedure in examining thick and thin malaria blood films	3.58	HC
allow the stained blood smears to dry properly before microscopic examination.	3.82	HC
check the expiration date of the Giemsa staining solution before use.	3.75	HC
clean the stained slides with tissue paper to remove the excess stains.	3.70	HC
cover the staining solutions after use to avoid evaporation.	3.68	HC
clean the staining area after every use.	3.77	HC
Sub-Mean	3.69	HC

Legend: HC = Highly Competent

As gleaned from Table 12, the level of competency of malaria microscopists along staining generated a mean rating of 3.69, described as highly competent. This means that the malaria microscopists have the adequate skills to perform staining of blood samples. This skill is so vital as according to Gulati, et. Al. (2013) a microscopic examination of an appropriately prepared and well-stained blood smear by a knowledgeable laboratory professional is necessary and clinically useful in a number of circumstances and for a variety of reasons.

Among the indicators, the microscopists were found to be highly competent in allowing the stained blood smears to dry properly before microscopic examination, with a mean rating of 3.82. This means that the respondents are so aware of the importance of observing the right protocols in allowing the blood film to dry in air on a drying rack or tray as not observing this process can lead to improper staining and visualization. Accordingly, the Center for Disease Control and Prevention stated that insufficiently dried smears (and/or smears that are too thick) can detach from the slides during staining. The risk is increased in smears made with anticoagulated blood. This finding further implies that the microscopists safeguard their diagnosis and prevent chaotic events that may occur by allowing the blood specimens to properly dry up before the conduct of analysis.

Slide Examination

Slide examination is a method that requires a subjective evaluation by trained, experienced diagnosticians. Malaria microscopy is a skill that requires considerable training, experience and practice to achieve and maintain proficiency. This skill is of such importance as, according to Nega et al. (2020), successful malaria elimination calls for rapid and accurate diagnosis of cases so that the patients can promptly be treated before the occurrence of transmission.

Table 6. *Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Slide Examination*

	Mean	DE
Examine the stained smears within 10 minutes after staining.	3.48	HC
Perform parasite counting on the thick film.	3.33	HC
Calculate parasite density correctly	3.20	C
Examine the thin smear for confirmation of parasite species and mixed infections.	3.38	HC
Perform parasite counting in 200 microscopic fields	3.28	HC
Count at least 200 Leucocytes in a smear	3.37	HC
Record and report malaria results accurately	3.67	HC
Sub-Mean	3.39	HC

Legend: HC = Highly Competent; C = Competent

As gleaned from Table 13, the malaria microscopists are described to be highly competent, based on the mean rating of 3.39, on slide examination. This shows that the respondents have attained the competency required of them especially on smears examination, reporting and recording the results, as well as in dealing with thick films. Good quality microscopy is critical for accurate detection and confirmation of malaria parasite infections.

It has been claimed that prompt parasitological detection and confirmation of parasite infections is recommended as an important pillar of malaria case management for improved care and treatment of patients (WHO, 2015). This highlights the fact that slide examination – including smears examination, parasite confirmation, among others – remains to be an essential skill all malaria microscopist need to possess. As to Yitbarek et al. (2016), despite the recent introduction of rapid diagnostic tests, good-quality microscopy and proper slide examination are still considered a reference test for malaria diagnosis.

Among the indicators, the respondents were found to have high level of competence in recording and reporting malaria results accurately, which generated a mean of 3.67. This means that respondents give prime attention to the correct encoding of results to ensure that correct diagnosis and treatment be made. This further implies that they recognize that the accuracy of surveillance for malaria depends on the correct administration, interpretation, adherence, recording and reporting of Rapid Diagnostic Tests for malaria (RDTs).

This result recognizes what the World Health Organization, in its Malaria Microscopy Standard Operating Procedure Guide Book, that states that proper recording and reporting of the results of microscopy examination of blood films is very important for the clinical management of malaria patients and for the reliability of malaria surveillance data, which are the basis for monitoring, evaluating and planning program interventions. This is supported by the claims of Siyam et al. (2021), stating that recording and reporting health data in facilities is the backbone of routine health information systems, which provide data collected by health facility workers during service provision.

However, the respondents were found to be competent on calculating parasite density correctly as evidenced by the mean rating of 3.20. This means that they, as compared to other indicators, have to be given more exposures or opportunities to master the skill of dealing with the act of counting the parasite density in the slides. The quantitation of malaria parasite density, as explained by Freat (2009) is an important component of laboratory diagnosis of malaria. Microscopy of Giemsa-stained thick blood films is the conventional method for parasite enumeration. Accurate and reproducible parasite counts are difficult to achieve, because of inherent technical limitations and human inconsistency. This is supported by another study that explains that accurate quantification of parasite density in the human host is essential for understanding the biology and pathology of malaria (Koepli et al., 2016).

Summary of the Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Microscopy Diagnostic Components

Malaria, according to World Health Organization, must be recognized promptly in order to treat the patient in time and to prevent further spread of infection in the community via local mosquitoes. In addition, malaria should be considered a potential medical emergency and should be treated accordingly. As such, a delay in diagnosis and treatment leads to death in most malaria patients in the United States (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, n.d.)

The competency of malaria microscopists in Ilocos Region was determined in this study using the found Microscopy Diagnostic Components. Overall, the respondents were rated a mean of 3.64, interpreted as highly competent. This results indicate that the respondents are knowledgeable and that their skills on the preparation, making malaria smears, staining, and slide examination makes them very capable in making early diagnosis of possible malaria cases. Furthermore, the results imply that the malaria microscopists are equipped with the necessary aptitude to perform malaria examinations thereby helping in the cause of malaria treatment and prevention in Ilocos Region.

Table 7. Summary Table of the Level of Competency of Malaria Microscopists along Microscopy Diagnostic Components

	Mean	DE
Preparation	3.77	HC
Making Malaria Smears	3.72	HC
Staining	3.69	HC
Slide Examination	3.39	HC
Grand Mean	3.64	HC

Legend: HC = Highly Competent

From the four components, the respondents registered the highest competency on the preparation which means that they recognize the fact that the laboratory and all its apparatuses need to be properly prepared – clean, safe, and secure – to avoid cross contamination and to minimize, if not to completely remove, all hazards and risks that may tamper the result of the microscopy. On the other hand, although still described as highly competent, the respondents were ranked least on doing slide examination. This means that they still perform accurate diagnosis of cases and do accurate recording and reporting of malaria results. However, the result may have been affected by their competency on calculating parasite density correctly.

Overall, the malaria microscopists from the Ilocos Region show a remarkable competence in detecting malaria cases as the overall competency mean signal that they perform within the standards as indicated in each of the components of microscopy diagnosis.

Challenges Encountered by Malaria Microscopists

Despite the many efforts to end the occurrence of malaria or totally end malaria cases worldwide, there are barriers hindering the implementation of malaria diagnosis and treatment strategies or in general, there are factors that have adversely influenced the overall malaria treatment and prevention program.

In this study, there were personal inadequacies and support inadequacies that may have affected the correct detection, and possible treatment, of malaria cases. In the study of Mosquera-Romero et al. (2018), they identified the lack of personnel and microscopy posts in this border area as the main barrier. A similar study conducted in China revealed that the insufficient capacity for malaria diagnosis at a lower level is one of the challenges to achieving and maintaining the goal of malaria elimination (Ding et al., 2018).

Table 8. Challenges Encountered by Malaria Microscopists

	Mean	DE
Inability to identify malaria parasites because of poor eyesight.	2.53	SI
Limited time of microscopy due to hectic schedule and multi-tasking of Medical Technologist.	2.18	SI
Obsolete/ Old Model of microscope	2.17	SI
Irregular Quality Assurance monitoring and supervision from the program coordinators.	2.20	SI
Overstained / Understained malarial smear.	2.33	SI
Low interest in malaria microscopy	2.03	SI
Lack of laboratory supplies to be used during microscopy such as objective oil, lens paper, and others.	2.43	SI
Unavailability of reference materials in malaria microscopy like manuals and bench aids	2.22	SI
Uncalibrated and unmaintained microscope.	2.37	SI
Deteriorated Malarial slides	2.08	SI

Legend: I = Intense, SI=Slightly Intense

While another study focused on the challenge of staff competence, they mentioned that providing opportunities to improve malaria microscopy ability would increase the overall job satisfaction of microscopists and eventually improve the quality of care (Matsumoto-Takahashi et. al. 2021).

Table 8 reflects the challenges encountered by malaria microscopists in Ilocos Region. Based on the table, top three challenges include the inability to identify malaria parasites because of poor eyesight (2.53), the lack of laboratory supplies to be used during microscopy such as objective oil, lens paper, and others described as slightly intense (2.43) and not calibrated and unmaintained microscope (2.37);

all of which are described to which is described to be slightly intense/challenging.

The results indicate that the challenges faced by the microscopists encompass a personal challenge as well as challenges related to supplies management and the classic problem on time management due to overlapping schedules. It could be further inferred that these challenges may appear to be very simple but may have lasting and grave effect if left unaddressed. The personal challenge, as it is the first among the indicators, indicate the need for the microscopists to also find time to attend to their personal health as poor eyesight can truly lead to misdiagnosis and eventually mistreatment of cases. The result may not be referring to the poor eyesight due to emerging medical conditions but maybe because of the so-called eye fatigue syndrome.

In fact, eye fatigue was listed as one of the most common occupational concerns of microscope users due to long working hours (Jain et. al. 2014). The researches then recommended that there is an immediate need for increasing awareness about the various occupational hazards and their irreversible effects to prevent them.

On the importance of good eyesight among microscopists, the study of Lin et al. (2019) revealed that the visual health of microscope workers is an important occupational health concern, and a previous study suggested an association between lighting problems (e.g., flashing light, insufficient lighting) and eye symptoms among cleanroom workers in the electronics industry.

In addition, the lack of laboratory supplies to be used during microscopy is also a pressing issue that need to be addressed. Shortages are affecting routine laboratory procedures and diagnostic testing which may hamper the efficient detection of malaria cases. Incomplete laboratory equipment and materials may gravely affect the procedures to be done. In another study using qualitative analysis, the results show that the laboratory supply shortages affected not only the timely acquisition of laboratory reagents and supplies but also the job satisfaction and well-being of laboratory personnel (Hilborne et al., 2022).

In relation to this, lack of equipment and supplies to be used inside the laboratory can also affect the quality of laboratory service provided by the technologists or microscopists. Quality laboratory service, as claimed by Mesfin, Taye, Belay, Ashenafi, and Girma (2017) is an essential component of health care system. They also concluded that poor resources provision is one of the major factors that affecting the quality of laboratory service.

Moreover, the use of not calibrated and unmaintained microscope was considered as one of the most pressing issues among the challenges raised can also result to inefficient diagnosis of malaria cases. The calibration of microscope is an essential part of working with cells as accuracy is important to effectively diagnose possible malaria cases. Using a microscope that is calibrated means that the same results will be produced on the exact same sample under the same conditions if you were to use an entirely different microscope that was also calibrated. The reason to calibrate is to get the most accurate measurement of sample. Accordingly, calibration is important because it helps ensure accurate measurements, and accurate measurements are foundational to the quality, safety.

Indeed, there are some pressing issues that are faced by microscopists and these challenges have to be properly given due actions to maintain high standard and quality service that can contribute to the overall eradication of malaria in the region.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Competency of the Microscopists on the Microscopy Diagnostic Components and the Respondents' Profile

Table 9 provides details on the relationship of the level of competency of the microscopists on the microscopic diagnostic components and the respondents' profile variables. From the table, it could be deduced that there is there exist low significant relationship between the level of competency of the microscopists and some of the profile variables.

Table 9. Significant Relationship between Level of Competency and Profile

Spearman's rho		OVERALL COMPETENCE	Age	Sex	HEA	YEARS IN SERVICE	STATUS OF EMPLOYMENT	RELEVANT TRAINING	POSITION
OVERALL COMPETENCE	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.098	-.233	.154	.189	-.040	.161	-.101
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.455	.073	.240	.148	.761	.220	.442
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
Age	Correlation Coefficient	.098	1.000	-.005	-.157	.494**	.031	.282	.097
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.455		.969	.230	.000	.816	.029	.463
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
Sex	Correlation Coefficient	-.233	-.005	1.000	.010	.011	.013	.137	.201
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.073	.969		.942	.936	.922	.296	.123
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
HEA	Correlation Coefficient	.154	-.157	.010	1.000	-.114	.100	.019	.126
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.240	.230	.942		.384	.445	.886	.336

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	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
YEARS IN SERVICE	Correlation Coefficient	.189	.494*	.011	-.114	1.000	.345*	.272*	-.182
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.148	.000	.936	.384		.007	.036	.164
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
STATUS OF EMPLOYMENT	Correlation Coefficient	-.040	.031	.013	.100	.345*	1.000	.107	-.069
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.761	.816	.922	.445	.007		.415	.601
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
RELEVAN TRAINING	Correlation Coefficient	.161	.282*	.137	.019	.272*	.107	1.000	.082
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.220	.029	.296	.886	.036	.415		.534
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60
POSITION	Correlation Coefficient	-.101	.097	.201	.126	-.182	-.069	.082	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.442	.463	.123	.336	.164	.601	.534	
	N	60	60	60	60	60	60	60	60

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Low significant relationship exists between age variable and years in service (.494), age and relevant trainings attended (.282), years in service and status of employment (.345), and years in service and relevant trainings attended (.272). These weak correlations imply that in a way the profile variable may have an impact to the overall competence of the microscopists in doing malaria microscopic examinations but this do not gravely impact their overall importance.

Furthermore, for instance, the age variable and years in service (.494) may be affecting the performance of the microscopists but this does not mean that as the microscopist grow old and stay longer in service, they become less competent. In addition, the weak correlation of age and relevant trainings attended (.282) may signify the need to attend upgrading seminars but the lack of opportunity to attend learning and professional development programs does not necessarily mean that they become less competent.

On the other hand, the years in service and status of employment established a weak association (.345) which connotes that the status of employment does not affect their years of stay as microscopists. Moreover, the years in service and relevant trainings attended also posted low correlation (.272) which signals that the competence of the microscopists may not be gravely impacted by the number of years they render and the number of trainings they have attended. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Significant Relationship between the Level of Competency of the Microscopists on the Microscopy Diagnostic Components and the Problems Encountered

Table 10 provides details on the relationship of the level of competency of the microscopists and the problems encountered. From the table, it could be deduced that there is no significant relationship between the level of competency of the microscopists and the problems encountered.

Table 10. *Significant Relationship between Level of Competency and Problems Encountered*

		Overall Competence	Challenges
Spearman's rho	Overall Competence	Correlation Coefficient	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	-.073
		N	.577
Challenges	Challenges	Correlation Coefficient	-.073
		Sig. (2-tailed)	1.000
		N	.577

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

This means that the skills of microscopists in preparing and analyzing slide examinations are not affected, in any way, by the problems they experience whether it is a personal concern or a concern that they experienced in dealing with the lack of materials or equipment to be used in diagnosis.

This simply suggests that the microscopists generally have a coping mechanism in dealing with these challenges or difficulties that do not necessarily gravely affecting their efficiency and general performance in doing microscopic analysis, recording, and reporting. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher concluded that the malaria microscopists in Region 1 come from varied but rich personal and professional background, are skilled and competent in performing malaria microscopic examination.

The malaria microscopists have experienced negligible challenges or difficulties and that these do not affect their performance as microscopists.

The performance of malaria microscopists in Region 1 is not affected by their age, professional background, training and professional engagements, and their current employment credentials and are not disturbed by some minor difficulties they encounter in their laboratory activities.

To further improve the abilities of the malaria microscopists in Region 1, an enhanced capability-building program was also concluded.

The researcher, after a thorough analysis of the research findings, recommends that the personal and professional profile of malaria microscopists be intensified by engaging to advanced education and attendance to more advanced and relevant trainings that can best contribute to the improvement of their competency on malaria detection and prevention.

The proposed capacity building program for the malaria microscopists in Region 1 can be adopted and be allotted a budget to provide them a timely a professional development program to improve their level of competence as microscopists. The said program can be adopted by the local Medical Technologists Association and be subjected to Professional Regulations Commission accreditation to ensure that CPD units be earned by the participants needed for the renewal of their individual PRC cards.

The Department of Health, to address challenges, should ensure that all available technical and professional support be accorded to the malaria microscopists in Region 1 for them to be properly guided in their role as first-line defenders against the outbreak of malaria in the region and that they need to endeavor to attend continuous professional education like enrolling in their master degree for them to be updated with the developments in their profession that can help them acquire greater competency while ensuring that their working environment including the equipment and apparatuses they utilize are constantly recalibrated and properly maintained.

The malaria microscopists are recommended to establish a strong partnership with the local government units to create more advocacy activities towards the total eradication of malaria in the region.

The malaria microscopists are also encouraged to undergo more exposures to DOH-accredited trainings especially on advanced methods of laboratory techniques to advance competence on malaria detection.

As a final point, do a similar study, on wider scope and perspectives, for further validation of the relationship of the profile and the level of competence and to check whether the competence of the microscopists can be improve through enhancement capability programs.

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